

Examining the Impact and Consequences of Data Integrity Violations in the Indian Pharmaceutical Sector

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Yogesh Binnar has 16+ years of experience in the pharmaceutical industry and is currently working as Head QA and RA in a drug manufacturing company. He has handled more than 100 customer audits. In addition, handled one USFDA audit successfully with VAI rating. He has also handled WHO GMP, and ISO 9001:2015 audits several times. He is a Maharashtra state FDA approved chemist in QC-Chemical and Instrumentation. He is well conversant with the regulatory requirements of the US, Europe, Canada, and ROW markets (CIS country, Uganda, etc). He has been responsible for the submission of more than 50 dossiers (CTD module) in the ROW market for different formulations. He is well experienced in the preparation of DMF type II and type IV.

Co-Author

Dr. Vinod Bhalla brings forty-seven years of leadership experience in renowned pharmaceutical companies (API, Formulations including sterile preparations, Biotechnology) in Quality, Regulatory, Projects, and Business management. The last position he held was President of Quality. He was responsible for establishing a strong QMS. In addition, he has handled and guided several pharmaceutical companies for successful 121 regulatory audits (USFDA, EQQM, EUGMP, MCC, TGA, etc.). It included 61 USFDA audits, quite a few without 483. He has been responsible for the preparation/review and submission of dossiers in CTD format both for API and for formulations for regulatory submissions and to the customers. He holds an APIC certification as an auditor and has conducted third-party audits across multiple European nations. He also guided WHO GMP and ISO 9001:2015 audits several times.

Abstract

This review examines recent data integrity issues within Indian pharmaceutical companies. Adherence to regulations regarding good documentation practices and data integrity is crucial, as both customers and regulatory agencies rely on the accuracy and reliability of data generated and stored by pharmaceutical companies. The ALCOA Plus principles are widely implemented to ensure data integrity within the industry. The objective of this study is to identify the frequency and impact of data integrity violations reported by the United State Food and Drug Administration on Indian pharmaceutical companies and to explore the consequences of these violations. The data for this analysis was sourced from the USFDA database, which included a review of 20 warning letters issued to pharmaceutical companies in India. The study also examines relevant guidelines on data integrity, including those from the WHO, USFDA, MHRA, and PIC/S. A comparison of data from 2023 and 2024 with the past 12 years reveals a noticeable increase in both warning letters and data integrity findings. Most of these issues are observed in the quality control and production departments. As a result, some companies have received IMPORT ALERT for the U.S. market barring them from supplying to the US affecting sales and the company's reputation. Further research is necessary to develop more

effective solutions and strategies to prevent data integrity violations. Despite the availability of numerous guidelines, ongoing research is recommended to enhance compliance and mitigate data integrity concerns.

Keywords

ALCOA +, USFDA, Warning letter, Data Integrity, cGMP, Quality Control.

INTRODUCTION

In the pharmaceutical industry, data integrity is a critical attribute in the development, manufacturing, and testing of drug products. Data integrity involves accuracy, consistency, and integrity of data throughout its entire duration, from collection and storage to analysis and reporting. This concept is essential in ensuring that pharmaceutical products are safe, effective, and of high quality. With the growing intricacies of drug development and evolving regulatory expectations, preserving data integrity has become an essential concern for pharmaceutical firms worldwide

DATA INTEGRITY PRINCIPLES^{1, 2, 3}

The key concepts underpinning data integrity are frequently represented by the acronym ALCOA+, where the first principle is Attributable followed by Legible, Contemporaneous, Original, and Accurate. These principles provide a foundation for developing effective data management practices:

- 1. Attributable:** Data must be traceable to the individual who generated it. This ensures accountability and allows for the verification of data authenticity. The person who has created the data must be a signatory so that it can be identified later also or during the review time that this person has created or generated the data.
In paper records, a signature with the person's name and date typically satisfies this requirement. For electronic records, the individual must enter data using their unique user ID, and the system used should maintain an audit trail or log, allowing the origin and history of the data to be traced at any time.
- 2. Legible, traceable, and permanent:** Data shall be legible and readable, whether it is in electronic or paper format. This principle helps to prevent misinterpretation and facilitates efficient inspection and assessment of the recorded information whenever required. There should not be overwritten, no pencil use, no marker, and no gel pan used in paper format, so that data will be reviewed and understood clearly whenever required. In an Electronic system, data can store with backup. Digital records are typically accessible or understandable only when viewed using the software program in which they were originally generated.
In electronic systems, this traceability should be documented via computer-generated audit trails. Electronic records can usually be interpreted correctly only with the specific application that was used to create them.
- 3. Contemporaneous:** Information must be documented immediately when it is produced. This principle ensures that the data reflects the actual conditions under which it was collected (the data is recorded at the time of activity only we can call as online or on time) and reduces the risk of discrepancies.
For instance, during sample preparation or weighing, details such as the sample's weight, date and time of measurement, operator's name, and the balance ID must be logged immediately at

the point of activity—not beforehand or afterward. For electronically stored information, these should be automatically date- and time-stamped. If hybrid systems are implemented, even temporarily, the assessment should address the potential risks and significance of system breaches, along with documented controls to mitigate these risks.

- 4. Original:** Data must be recorded in its original form; Original data refers to the initial collection of information, and any subsequent modifications must be thoroughly recorded and documented. This principle helps preserve data accuracy and makes any modifications easily traceable.
- 5. Accurate:** This concept safeguards the reliability of data while ensuring that any updates can be clearly tracked. Accuracy is vital for making reliable conclusions and confirming that decisions are based on valid information.

The “+” in “ALCOA+” signifies extra principles. Data and metadata must be comprehensive i.e. **complete**, allowing for the reconstruction of any event. **Consistency** in data means they are produced uniformly each time. **Durability** secures that record remain intact throughout their retention period. Lastly, **accessibility** indicates that data are easily available to employees for reference.

Figure 1: ALCOA Plus

Regulatory Frameworks and Guidelines^{1, 2, 3}

Various regulatory frameworks and guidelines govern data integrity for the pharmaceutical industry:

WHO TRS (Technical Report Series) 1033 – Annexure No. 4: WHO Guideline on data integrity in 2021, US FDA has established guidelines such as 21 CFR Part 11, which addresses electronic records and electronic signatures and also in part 211(211.68, 211.100 and 211.160, 211.180, 211.188, 211.194, and 212.60(g)) which include the requirement for data integrity. This regulation outlines requirements to secure accuracy, authenticity, protection of digital information.

PIC/S GUIDANCE on good practices for data management and integrity in regulated GMP/GDP, environments in July 2021, EC EudraLex Volume 4 has set requirements for documentation³.

Figure 2a: Major Regulatory Guidelines

Figure 2b: Abbreviation of Agency

Examples of Data integrity concerns, among others ¹¹

- Falsifying data
- Deleting data without justification
- Entering incorrect data
- Using inaccurate or fabricated dates
- Making false statements, omitting facts, or providing misleading information that does not reflect actual events
- Submitting data that is unreliable or not verifiable
- Presenting previously existing data as new or original
- Maintaining duplicate or redundant records
- Failing to store electronic as well as physical data properly
- Not documenting activities in real-time or immediately after they occur
- Altering analytical procedures or data to achieve desired results
- Performing repeated analyses on the same sample without valid reasons
- Attempting to modify poorly defined or unclear analytical methods
- Ignoring or disregarding failed test results without proper explanation
- Making process changes without proper justification or documentation

MATERIALS AND METHODS⁴⁻³⁴

The researcher scholar has reviewed many articles, warning letters which was issued by the USFDA to drugs company, and regulatory guidelines for Data Integrity like WHO TRS, USFDA, and EU GMP and surfed proposed research-related sites to gather more information for review and to get knowledge in the same filed and to grasp the thought process of the researcher. In this study, data integrity breaches were evaluated on the basis of the US FDA warning letters issued from January 2023 to Nov 2024 to Indian pharmaceutical companies. Also, data for year 2010 to 2022 is taken only for comparison (table 1). The analysis was conducted by examining observations in these notification letters departments and only pharmaceutical industries are taken for analysis, other industries may have warning letters like food or medical devices which are not included in this study (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Methodology

Table 1 shows total no. of USFDA inspections from the year 2019 to 2024 in India².

Year	Number of Indian Pharma Companies Received Warning Letter till 30th Nov 2024				Number of Data Integrity Observations			
	2010	2018	2019	2024	2010	2018	2019	2024
2010	4	2018	9	2010	1	2018	3	
2011	5	2019	25	2011	5	2019	3	
2012	3	2020	14	2012	2	2020	3	
2013	9	2021	7	2013	7	2021	0	
2014	9	2022	3	2014	14	2022	4	
2015	12	2023	12	2015	7	2023	16	
2016	11	2024	8	2016	13	2024	13	
2017	14				NA			
Total	145				94			

Figure 4: Graphical presentation for warning letter FY 2010 - 2024

Table 1: Number of warning

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There has been a rise in the number of data integrity related warning letters issued by the USFDA, as shown in Table 2 and Figure 5. In the last five years, there has been increased in data integrity concern went up from 13 between 2018 and 2022 to 16 in 2023. By November 30, 2024, there have been 13 issues reported. However, some inspections in India may still be happening, and their results are not included in this data.

Graph 5 shows the quantity of observations in each department, along with their percentage contribution (See Graph 5). This analysis draws on twelve warning letters released in 2023 and 8 issued in 2024 for data integrity violations (See Table 2).

Table 2: Number of observations of warning letters department-wise for 2024 & 2023.

Department	Total Observed Cases	Percentage (%) of Observation	Number of Finding because of Data Integrity	Data Integrity %
Year 2024				
Quality Assurance	11	21.57	1	1.96
Quality Control	20	39.22	11	21.57
Production	17	33.33	1	1.96
Warehouse	1	1.96	0	0
Maintenance	2	3.92	0	0
Total	51	100.00	13	25.49
Year 2023				
Quality Assurance	11	22.45	2	4.08
Quality Control	15	30.61	13	26.53
Production	20	40.82	1	2.04
Warehouse	1	2.04	0	0
Maintenance	2	4.08	0	0
Total	49	100.00	16	32.65

Figure 5: DI presentation FY 2024 and 2023

Out of the 29 data integrity observations in 2023 and 2024, 24 were attributed to the quality control department only.

Data integrity breaches within Quality Control reflect a failure to uphold the obligation of ensuring drug products are produced in line with CGMP standards and fulfill the specified specifications for identity, strength, quality, and purity (21 CFR 211.22). Additionally, It was noted that failure to guarantee that all necessary test data, required to confirm compliance with established specifications and standards, were properly documented (21 CFR 211.194(a)).

A review of data integrity issues revealed that QC did not implement adequate controls over computers or related systems to ensure that only authorized personnel could make changes to the control records or other related documents (21 CFR 211.68(b)). For instance, the QC analyst had administrative privileges i.e. capability of alter results (copy, paste, delete), dates, audit trails were not enabled on the chromatographic systems/computers. QC failed to ensure the dependability of data concerning the quality of the produced medicines. This includes failing to maintain the integrity of analytical testing data, issues with privileges granted to computerized systems, inadequate laboratory investigations and interrupted chromatographic sequences. Additionally, KF raw data and analytical balance paper printouts were destroyed, laboratory records were incomplete and inaccurate, raw laboratory data was missing and could not be provided during the inspection, and there were issues with chromatographic data integration. In addition, working and reference standards management, stability testing issues e.g. stability schedule not adhered to, and raw data went unrecorded contemporaneously. All these observations pointed out the manipulation of data and outcomes. There have been instances wherein the laboratory staff admitted the fabrication of results e.g. results of environment monitoring (EM) by microbiology.

There was an absence of control by the Quality Unit wherein the duplicate records were created and initial CGMP documentation were destroyed by tearing / shredding. These included analytical worksheets, laboratory incident forms, training records, batch production and packing records, calibration records, etc. Besides this, pre-printed uncontrolled blank analysis records and incident documentation, and non-conformance forms were kept in laboratory drawers and cabinets without proper access restrictions and control measures.

All the above instances pointed out the failure of the QMS and resulted in 483 observations followed by notification or alert letters and import alerts.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The author and co-authors played a key role in the contribution to the creation, along with in the collection, analysis, and interpretation of the data.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors confirm that they have no competing interests related to this work.

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CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS AND UPCOMING OPPORTUNITIES

Data dependability is severely compromised when an instance of failure to maintain the complete record or accurate records of test results, or conditions associated with all tests. Furthermore, the absence of reliable data compromises the QA's capability to enforce its control ensuring compliance with applicable standards.

Customers depend on the accuracy of laboratory records that are created, approved, and managed by companies. It is crucial to enforce stringent management of CGMP electronic records as well as paper record so that firm can ensure that there is no fabrication, manipulation

like additions, deletions in the original data and changes to information in the company's records are authorized and properly documented.

Further research in this field is necessary to prevent data integrity issues that could cause receiving warning letters and import alerts. Additionally, such studies are vital for enhancing quality assurance and enhancing customers' confidence.

SUMMARY

Over the past 15 years, regulatory bodies have sent warning letters to over 100 Indian pharmaceutical companies, highlighting several issues related to data integrity and management. However, the number of warning letters issued in FY 2023 & FY 2024 is significantly higher as compared to the previous years. The quality control department plays major role in the prevention of 483 observations and warning letters as a substantial number of data integrity concerns are being reported.

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